

ISic0587

I.Sicily inscription 0587

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance

'In S. Marci oppido extra pomerium in via Caturelli' (CIL)

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, San Marco d'Alunzio, lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Augusto · divi · f(ilio)

2. pontif(ici) · max(imo)

3. municipium

Apparatus

Text of CIL, after Gualtherus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491844

EDCS 22100582

Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 1988. *La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano.* *ANRW.* 2.11.1: 3-89. At 48

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